

EFFECT OF MONOTHERAPIES AND COMBINATIONAL THERAPIES OF KELOIDS AND HYPERTROPHIC SCARS RECURRENCE PREVENTION, SYMPTOMATIC RELIEF AND REMODELLING

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ABSTRACT

Keloids and Hypertrophic scars illustrate fibroproliferative conditions which have a high recurrence rate are the main problem. This systematic review assesses the recurrence, efficiency, effectiveness and safety outcome by using different surgical and non-surgical therapies that include corticosteroids, immunomodulators, vitamin D, cryotherapy, lasers, intralesional drug combinations and postoperative radiotherapy. Among all the therapies, early multimodal interventions and combination therapies have the best outcomes when compared to other treatments like monotherapies. When the radiotherapy is performed after post-excision, it has the lowest recurrence rate, as in the case of scar parameters, combination intralesional regimens and laser assisted steroid therapies has significant improvements. This review emphasizes the weight of choosing treatment approaches based on keloid chronicity, lesion characteristics and anatomical position of the keloid.

KEYWORDS: Keloids, Recurrence, monotherapies, combinational therapies.

INTRODUCTION

Keloids are benign fibroproliferative tumours that increase beyond the wound boundaries because of dysregulated collagen metabolism and persistent inflammation.^[1] Their treatment remains challenging, demonstrated by recurrence rates ranging from 30-80% even after

surgical removal.^[9] Various monotreatment such as cryotherapy, intralesional corticosteroids and laser therapy-offer slight improvement, however recurrence and adverse effects remain similar.^[1,2] Recently, integrated approach associates pharmacologic, physical, and surgical interventions have obtain prominence to increase therapeutic stability.^[5,6,7,8] This systematic review observance and evaluate 9 clinical studies that gives Various hypertrophic scar and keloid treatments to recognise the most effective predictors and modalities of treatment effective ness.

METHODOLOGY

Search Strategy and Study Selection

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systemic Reviews and Meta Analysis) 2020 guidelines to evaluate the Recurrence prevention, Symptomatic relief and Remodelling of Keloids and Hypertrophic scars. An extensive search was conducted in electronic databases such as PubMed, and Google scholar. The search utilized keywords such as Keloids, Recurrence, monotherapies, combinational therapies and in combination with Boolean operators (AND, OR) to maximize the retrieval of relevant literature. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs), cohort studies, case-control studies, Interventional study, observational studies that reported recurrence prevention, remodelling of the keloids and hypertrophic scars and symptomatic relief of the subjects with keloids and hypertrophic scars were considered for inclusion criteria. Articles between September 2012 and August 2025 were considered for the review in order to reflect the most recent advancements in the field.

Study Inclusion and Screening Process

Three reviewers screened titles and abstracts separately for relevance. Full texts of potentially relevant articles were screened against predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria aimed at the contribution of the Effect of Monotherapies and Combinational Therapies of Keloids and Hypertrophic scars Recurrence prevention, Symptomatic relief and Remodelling. The process of selection is represented in a PRISMA flowchart Figure 1.

Data extraction

Questionnaires are used to extract important and essential information from studies that are included. Which includes, study design and population, methods used for assessment and results. The data which is presented in table 1.

Quality Assessment

For determining methodological rigor and reliability of the findings, quality appraisal was conducted using Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal tools relevant to the research design.

JBI Checklist for Cohort Studies

Three reviewers independently assessed all studies. Discrepancies were addressed by discussion. Studies that met high or moderate quality standards with the appropriate JBI tool were included in the synthesis only to guide sound conclusions.

DISCUSSION

Overview of main findings

Among the nine studies that we reviewed, combination therapies gave better improvement when compared to mono therapy in terms of scar improvement and recurrence reduction. Vitamin D and cryotherapy are showing improvement, but those are incomplete in pigmentation and remodelling the keloids.^[4,1] Laser treatments like PDL (Pulsed Dye Laser) and Nd: YAG (Neodymium- doped yttrium aluminum garnet) laser were highly effective and recommended, especially when combined with intralesional steroids.^[8,2] Intralesional combination drugs such as IPL (Intense Pulsed Light) + TAC (Triamcinolone acetonide) and TAC + 5 FU (5-Fluorouracil) plus hyaluronidase have incredible and great outcomes with fewer side effects, placing them as the best non-surgical options^[6,7] post-excisional radiotherapy shows the best improvement in the case of recurrence of keloids, especially because the electron beam administration has the lowest recurrence rate of all the therapies.^[5,9] Anatomical pressure, lesion chronicity, and residual inflammation are considered as main predictors of recurrence^[1,2,9]

Cryotherapy in keloid management

Cryotherapy leads to continued lesion growth flattening, attaining 58% improvement after six sessions of cryotherapy. In addition to that, other key improvements like symptomatic relief from pruritus and pain. Response to the therapy is primarily determined by thickness and duration, with thin (<0.6cm) and early (<3 years) keloids determining the most favourable outcomes. Side effects that include hypo pigmentation, especially with darker skin tones.^[1]

Long-Pulsed 1064-nm Nd: YAG Laser

Neodymium-doped yttrium aluminium garnet (YAG) laser therapy majorly Decreased scar scores in both Keloids and hypertrophic scars though Hypertrophic scars reacted Completely. Keloids on the anterior chest showed a low response and more recurrence. Reaching 52.9% despite long last treatment. Remaining sclerosis and erythema strongly predicted re-appeared.^[2]

Surgical Excision Followed by Methylprednisolone vs topical imiquimod

Imiquimod-treated and 50% of reappearance occurred in 37 .5% of steroid-treated lesions, a diversity that was not statistically important. Imiquimod caused in more local adverse effects such as erosion, and erythema, although all were spontaneous resolution. The study was weakened but recommended comparatively efficacy between the two post-excisional topical managements.^[3]

Systematic and intralesional vitamin D therapy

Vitamin D sufficient and insufficient groups showed significant improvements in pliability and vascularity from the intralesional vitamin D injection, but there is no improvement in the pigmentation and thickness of keloid. From this we can conclude that there is no influence of the presence of vitamin D will affect the scar development and scar severity, some side effects are occurred, but they resolved after some period of time.^[4]

Surgery with or without adjuvant radiotherapy and pharmacologic injections

Combination therapy shows more improvement i.e. surgery plus radiotherapy has 93.9% effectiveness and surgery without radiotherapy has 55.6% improvement. Lesion size and age are the other characteristics that influence it, but in this study, the treatment plan was the only characteristic that predicted the recurrence rate. Long-term follow-ups needed, i.e. up to 3 years were recommended because as recurrence occurs at any time.^[5]

Intense Pulsed Light +Intralesional Triamcinolone vs. Steroid Monotherapy

Combination treatment reached Importantly greater developments in all pigmentation, VSS (Vancouver Scar Scale) domains -vascularity, pliability, are height and no recurrences over follow-up, during steroid monotherapy had two recurrences. Patient satisfaction results were also higher in the combination group.^[6]

Triple Intralesional Therapy (TAC + 5-FU + Hyaluronidase)

Triple therapy generated good Recovery in all scar parameters compared with TAC monotherapy, with VSS results rising to 54.5% by week 12 vs. 36.6% for monotherapy. 3 patients in the combination group attained complete flattening, no recurrences occurred in either group through follow-up. None did in the monotherapy group.^[7]

8.595 nm pulses laser plus IL TAC vs IL TAC alone

Combination therapy results in greater improvement in pigmentation, VSS reduction, and patient satisfaction. The studies, like histopathological studies, showed better collagen organization and reduced keloid collagen after combination therapy when compared with alone therapy. Side effects are self-resolving.^[8]

Post-Excisional Electron Beam Radiotherapy

Early radiotherapy (<72 hours post-excision) gives an 81.1% recurrence rate, whereas 6 of 7 recurrences occurred during radiotherapy started after 72 Hours. High-tension anatomical regions exhibited importantly high recurrence. Maternal family history gives a statistically important Association with keloid development.^[9]

Clinical Implications

These 9 studies collectively assist a multimodal, specific approach to hypertrophic scar and keloid management. Essential invasive combinations (e.g., 5-FU ± intralesional steroid ± hyaluronidase, IPL + TAC, PDL + IL-TAC, Nd: YAG in contact mode) give faster, greater development in pliability, vascularity and height versus monotherapies, and frequently better patient satisfaction, mainly when started early for thinner/less mature lesions. Surgical excision single shows high recurrence. Adjuvant radiotherapy (postoperative protocols or electron beam), together with pharmacologic or radiation approaches, notably decrease the recurrence. Topical immunomodulators (imiquimod) and local vitamin D show assurance as an addition to scar remodelling and symptom relief but need larger validation. Indicators of poorer outcome include long lesion duration, high mechanical-tension sites, greater thickness (chest, anterior, shoulders), remaining redness /induration at the end of therapy, and delayed postoperative radiotherapy; these should guide treatment selection and follow-up intensity.

Strengths of the obtainable literature

The main body of the evidence, which has split scar intraindividual designs, randomized controlled trials, large retrospective cohorts and prospective comparative studies, provided a

range of methodologies and clinical outcomes like scar scales, VSS, histopathology, haemoglobin indices, pigmentation and satisfaction of the subject. Several study reports have head-to-head comparison and have mechanistic rationales like pharmacologic pathways, laser wavelength, and tissue targets, which improve the value of clinical practice.

Limitations and gaps

Most trials have small-to-moderate sample size, single -centre with short follow-up (≤ 12 months), heterogeneous outcome measures, limited blinding and various comparator choices (e.g., topical steroid vs intralesional gold standard). Skin-type classification and standardized recurrence definitions are often inadequate. Continuing safety (pigmentary sequelae, radiation carcinogenesis) and expensive, inadequate residual data, large, systemized endpoints with multiple centre RCTS and ≥ 3 -year follow-up are required.

Table 1: Data extraction from the collected studies.

Name & year	Country	Study design	Sample size	Study population	Agerange/mean age	Prs calculation method	Groups
Interventional study							
Cryotherapy in Treatment of Keloids: Evaluation of Factors Affecting Treatment Outcome, 2012	India (Study at Lady Hardinge Medical College, New Delhi)	Hospital-based interventional study	30 patients (12 males, 18 females)	Patients (>12 years) with untreated keloids; excluded if treated in past 12 weeks or contraindicated for cryotherapy	Mean 27.5 ± 7.24 years (Range 12–41 years)	Not applicable (study measured % flattening, thickness reduction, patient satisfaction score)	Cryotherapy with two 15-sec freeze–thaw cycles every 4 weeks; max 6 sessions or ≥75% flattening
Retrospective cohort study							
Nd: YAG Laser Treatment for Keloids and Hypertrophic Scars, 2014	Japan (Nippon Medical School, Tokyo)	Retrospective cohort study	102 patients (23 males, 79 females)	Japanese patients with keloids (64 cases) and hypertrophic scars (38 cases); previously treated for >1 year without improvement; large/thick keloids excluded.	Mean age: 34.8 years (range not mentioned)	Not applicable. (Study used Japan Scar Workshop Scale 2011 for evaluation).	Long-pulsed 1064 nm Nd: YAG laser, contact mode. • Spot size 5 mm, energy 65–75 J/cm ² , pulse 250 μs, 2 Hz. • 3 passes per session unless pain. • Treatment every 3–4 weeks for 1 year. Groups: keloids (64) vs hypertrophic scars (38).
Randomized double blinded clinical trail							
Ricciardi AS et al., 2025	Brazil.	Randomized, double-blind, matching-lesion (self-paired) clinical trial. Unit of	10 patients (20 lesions) enrolled; 8 patients (16 lesions) completed 1-year follow-up (2 patients	Adults 18–70 y with ≥2 keloid lesions (phototypes III–VI). Most were ear keloids (8 patients = 16 ear keloids); 1 patient upper limb (2 lesions); 1 chest (2 lesions).	Mean 21.9 ± 4.8 years; range 18–31 years.	Not applicable / not reported (no PRS or genetic risk score reported).	All lesions surgically excised then randomized by paired lesion: (A) topical 5% imiquimod cream nightly for 8 weeks; (B) topical 0.1% methylprednisolone aceponate cream nightly for

		analysis = lesion (paired lesions per patient).	missed 1-yr visit).	Exclusion: pregnancy, recent retinoids, ncontrolled comorbidity, BMI>30, smokers, immunosuppression, certain anatomic sites.			8 weeks (placebo blinding via identical tubes).
Case control							
Hassan AR et al., 2025	Egypt & Saudi Arabia (multicentre authorship; study conducted in Egypt)	Clinical trial on 30 patients; divided by vitamin D level into two treatment groups: systemic + intralesional vs intralesional only.	30 patients (15 in Group I, 15 in Group II).	Patients aged 12–50 years with keloids or hypertrophic scars attending dermatology OPD. Excluded: <12 or >50 years, systemic skin disorders, receiving other keloid treatments, already on Vitamin D supplements.	Group I: 12–39 years (mean 20.5 ± 8.4) Group II: 12–33 years (mean 21.9 ± 7.2)	PRS not used / Not applicable.	Group I (Vitamin D deficient/insufficient): Monthly systemic Vitamin D3 injection (200,000 IU) for 3 months + calcium Intralesional vitamin D injections. Group II (Vitamin D sufficient): Intralesional Vitamin D injections only Dose: 0.3 mL of 200,000 IU cholecalciferol (non-diluted) per session Total 4 sessions, 2 weeks apart.
Yasuda K et al., 2025	Japan (Hyogo College of Medicine)	Case–control genetic association study evaluating the role of SERPINB3 rs15286 polymorphism in keloid patient's vs	63 keloid patients + 200 controls. Patients split by genotype: AA (n=28), AG (n=23), GG (n=12).	Japanese patients with clinically diagnosed keloids attending dermatology department. Controls = healthy volunteers with no keloid history. No major systemic disease. Demographics recorded.	Mean age: Patients = 48.2 ± 15.4 yrs; Controls = 47.8 ± 18.5 yrs. (Age range not explicitly stated.) PRS Calculation	No polygenic risk score (PRS) used. Only single SNP (rs15286) genotyping.	DNA extracted from blood. Genotyping using TaqMan SNP assay for rs15286. Groups: AA vs AG vs GG genotypes. Compared: keloid onset age, BMI, ear-tumour occurrence, pain/itching severity, height of lesion, plasma SERPINB3 level.

		controls. 63- keloid subjects and 200 controls.					
Prospective observational study							
Alternative treatment for recurrent keloids: initial clinical experience with Rhenium- 188 using a specialized device, 2025	South Africa (University of Pretoria, Steve Biko Academic Hospital; additional collaborators from Germany)	Prospective clinical observational study / initial clinical experience study	29 patients, 59 lesions treated	Adults (>18 yrs) with recurrent/intractable keloids unresponsive to other therapies (surgery, steroids, radiation)	Mean age 40.33 years (range 25– 50 yrs)	N/A (study not related to polygenic risk scores)	Rhenium-188 (188Re) topical therapy using Onbeat specialized applicator system. All patients received personalized single-session dose targeting 30 Gy to deepest lesion margin (1–3 mm) Measurements of lesion area, activity applied, treatment time done with VARSKIN 5 software
Randomized control trail							
Efficacy and safety of intra- lesional triple combination versus intralesional triamcinolone acetoneide for the treatment of eloids: A randomised controlled trial, 2025	India (Aarupadai Veedu Medical College & Hospital, Puducherry)	Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT) → Two-arm parallel group Triple combination vs. Triamcinolone monotherapy	72 patients (36 per group)	Adults ≥18 years with untreated keloids (any site, any duration). Excluded: pregnancy, lactation, organ disease, immunocompromised, follow-up issues.	Group A mean age: 29.83 ± 13.69 yrs Group B mean age: 28.31 ± 14.07 yrs	N/A (not a genetic or PRS study)	Group A (Triple Combination): Triamcinolone acetoneide 0.4 mL (40 mg/mL) 5-fluorouracil 0.6 mL (250 mg/5 mL) Hyaluronidase 1500 IU, Group B (Monotherapy): Intralesional Triamcinolone acetoneide (40 mg/mL) Treatment frequency: every 3 weeks × 4 sessions or until flattening.
Efficacy of Combined	Thailand (Ramathibodi	Prospective, evaluator-	25 transgender men with 35	Transgender men on testosterone therapy	Mean age: 32.8 ± 6.91 years	N/A (not genetics or PRS)	Split-side randomization: Intervention: 595-nm Pulsed

595-nm Pulsed Dye Laser and Intralesional Corticosteroids vs Intralesional Corticosteroids Alone..., 2025	Hospital, Mahidol University, Bangkok)	blinded, intra-individual split-sided Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)	symmetric pairs of postmastectomy hypertrophic scars/keloids	Postmastectomy HTS or keloids located on nipple/inframammary area Ages ~33 years		study)	Dye Laser (PDL) + Intralesional Triamcinolone (IL TAC),– PDL: 7-mm spot, 5–7 J/cm ² , 0.45 ms pulse, single pass,– IL TAC: 10 mg/mL, 0.3–1 mL depending on scar size Control: IL TAC monotherapy 4 monthly treatment sessions for both sides
Retrospective clinical study							
Postoperative Electron Beam Radiotherapy for Keloids: Treatment Outcome and Factors Associated with Occurrence and Recurrence, 2015	South Korea (Chonbuk National University Medical School & Hospital)	Retrospective clinical study (review of cases treated 2006–2012)	30 patients with 37 keloid lesions	Male: 7 patients (8 lesions) Female: 23 patients (29 lesions) Age range: 11–66 years, mean 23.9 years Lesion sites: earlobe (59.5%), helix (16.2%), shoulder (10.8%), chest wall (8.1%), abdomen (5.4%)	11–66 years; Mean 23.8–23.9 years	N/A (not a genetic PRS study, though family history is assessed)	All lesions: Surgical excision + postoperative electron beam radiotherapy using 6-MeV electrons Radiation doses: 12 Gy for 11 lesions 15 Gy for 20 lesions 16 Gy for 3 lesions 18 Gy for 3 lesions Dose delivered every other day in 3–4 Gy fractions Start of radiotherapy: Within 24 h: 24 lesions 24–72 h: 6 lesions >72 h: 7 lesions (significantly associated with recurrence)

name & year	Follow up duration	Limitations	Assessment method	Key findings
interventional study				
cryotherapy in treatment of keloids: evaluation of factors affecting treatment outcome, 2012	<3 yrs (A), 3–6 yrs (B), >6 yrs (C)	Small sample size, uncontrolled study; requires larger comparative studies	Vernier caliper measurements (size, thickness), firmness, symptoms, serial photography, patient satisfaction scale (0–3)	Average flattening:30.77% (3 sessions), 58.13% (6sessions) Duration & thickness strongly predicted outcome (P=0.000 and 0.023) Recent onset (<3yrs) responded best (68.5% flattening) 76.67% achieved good–excellent response (≥50% flattening) Site and etiology did not affect results Common side effects:pain+ dyspigmentation
retrospective cohort study				
nd: yag laser treatment for keloids and hypertrophic scars, 2014	6 months after stopping treatment; some cases followed up to 30 months or 3 years.	Keloids respond less effectively than hypertrophic scars. Recurrence occurs if any redness/induration remains. Mechanical tension on skin reduces treatment success. No control group; retrospective design.	Japan Scar Workshop Scar Scale 2011: induration, elevation, redness, surrounding erythema, spontaneous pain, pain on pressure, itching. Measured at each session.	Hypertrophic scars responded better than keloids. Recurrence occurred if even small residual redness/induration persisted. Significant improvements in elevation, redness, induration, itch, and pain over 1 year. Case findings: total scar scores improved (e.g., 15→3; 10→1). • Contact-mode Nd: YAG may be superior to non-contact (Genesis mode) for thick scars
randomized double blinded clinical trail				
ricciardi as et al., 2025	Clinical follow-up visits up to 48 weeks (1 year); primary outcome = recurrence at 1 year.	Clinical exam and dimensional measurements (length, width, thickness); two independent evaluators (interobserver Kappa = 100% for final 16 lesions); patient	Small sample (underpowered vs planned 20 lesions final analysis), 2 patients lost to one-year clinical exam, majority lesions were ear keloids (limited	Recurrence at 1 year: imiquimod group 3/8 lesions (37.5%) vs methylprednisolone group 4/8 lesions (50%); difference not statistically significant (p>0.05). Imiquimod caused more local side effects (erythema 6/8, erosion 5/8, pain 4/8) vs none in steroid group (all p <0.05 for those side effects). Overall efficacy of surgery+imiquimod was not statistically inferior to surgery+steroid; authors

		questionnaire for pain/itching and satisfaction (0/1), histopathology and special stains described; statistical tests: paired t-test, McNemar test.	generalizability), used topical steroid instead of intralesional triamcinolone (gold standard), short sample diversity.	recommend further larger studies.
case control				
hassan ar et al., 2025	1 month after last injection; no recurrence during follow-up.	Short follow-up (only 1-monthpost treatment) Small sample size (n=30) No control group without treatment Variability in occupations, scar duration, and sites Systemic vitamin D used despite no baseline severity differences (discussed by authors).	Vancouver Scar Scale (vascularity, pliability, pigmentation, height); vitamin D levels via ELISA; statistical tests: paired & unpaired t-test, chi-square, Pearson correlation.	Vitamin D deficiency did not affect scar formation or severity (p>0.05). Both groups improved significantly in vascularity, pliability, and total VSS score (p<0.05). No improvement in pigmentation or height. No significant difference between Group I & II— intralesional vitamin D effective regardless of baseline vitamin D status. Side effects mild and temporary (pain, erythema, swelling).
yasuda k et al., 2025	None (cross-sectional genetic study).	Single SNP; no genome-wide analysis. Small sample size for genotype subgrouping (especially GG). Cross-sectional—no causal inference. Only Japanese population → limited	Clinical examination of keloid features. Measurement of lesion height. Pain/itching via numeric rating scale (0–10). Plasma SERPINB3 concentration via	GG genotype strongly associated with early-onset keloids (<20 yrs) (p=0.004). GG genotype showed highest pain and itch scores among all groups (p<0.05). GG also correlated with greater keloid height (p<0.05). Plasma SERPINB3 levels were significantly higher in keloid patients than controls (p<0.001). Authors conclude rs15286 polymorphism may

		generalizability.	ELISA. Logistic regression, ANOVA, chi-square analysis used.	contribute to early-onset and severe keloids.
prospective observational study				
alternative treatment for recurrent keloids: initial clinical experience with rhenium-188 using a specialized device, 2025	Median 37 months (range 11–59 months) with follow-ups at 2, 4, 8, 24 weeks, and 12 months	Small sample size Irregular follow-up in some cases Limited subjective outcome tools (QoL)questionnaires incomplete) Single-center preliminary study	Clinical photographs Lesion measurement (height & diameter) Categorized outcomes: complete response, partial response, no response, progression Patient-reported symptoms (pain,itching	Complete response in 72% of lesions Recurrence rate 7% after median 37 months Hypopigmentation common long-term side effect Effective alternative for keloids resistant to other therapies Single-session treatment feasible and well tolerated
randomized control trail				
efficacy and safety of intralesional triple combination versus intralesional triamcinolone acetonide for the treatment of keloids: a randomised controlled trial,2025	Total: 24 weeks (3 months post-treatment) Visits: baseline, 3, 6, 9 weeks → monthly × 3 months.	Small sample size Single-centre trial Short follow-up (3 months) No blinding Lacked patient-reported outcomes (QoL measures)	Vancouver Scar Scale (VSS): vascularity, pigmentation, pliability, height Photographs Clinical examination Pain assessment (post-procedure)	Group A (triple therapy) showed significantly greater improvement in VSS at all time points vs. Group B (p<0.05). Final improvement: – Group A: 54.55% – Group B: 36.65% Better improvement in vascularity, pigmentation, pliability, height in Group A. Safety: Minimal pain only lasting a few hours No atrophy, hypopigmentation, ulceration, infection Recurrence: No recurrence in either group during 24-week follow-up.
efficacy of combined 595-nm pulsed dye laser and intralesional corticosteroids vs intralesional	Follow-up at 1, 3, and 6 months after final treatment (total approx. 10 months)	Small sample size All scars on anterior chest → limited generalizability Histology only from one participant * All	Vancouver Scar Scale (VSS) (primary outcome) Melanin index Haemoglobin index Scar roughness (Antera 3D device)	Combined PDL + IL TAC produced significantly greater improvement in: VSS after 2 sessions (p=0.012) Improvement persisted at 1 and 3 months post-treatment (p=0.002 and p=0.001) Melanin index improvements significant through all

corticosteroids alone..., 2025		participants on testosterone (may influence scarring)	Participant satisfaction (VAS) Histopathology in one participant Adverse event monitoring	visits, No serious or permanent adverse events Patient satisfaction significantly higher for combined therapy (p=0.005) Histology: reduced keloidal collagen + increased new collagen & elastic fibers at 6 months
retrospective clinical study				
postoperative electron beam radiotherapy for keloids: treatment outcome and factors associated with occurrence and recurrence, 2015	Minimum 6 months; median 27.4 months (range 9–51 months)	Retrospective study design Small sample size Site distribution uneven (majority ear lesions) No standardized cosmetic/quality-of-life scoring system No randomization or control group	Clinical recurrence evaluation Lesion characteristics (location, tension region) Timing of radiotherapy Radiation dose Family history analysis (maternal vs paternal) Side effects (acute dermatitis, hyperpigmentation)	Overall success (recurrence-free): 81.1% Recurrence rate: 18.9% 6 of 7 recurrences occurred when radiotherapy was started >72 hours post-surgery (p<0.0001) High tension areas (shoulder, chest, abdomen) had significantly more recurrence (p=0.010) Family history common but not significantly associated with recurrence; however, maternal transmission significantly more common (p=0.033) Side effects: mild acute dermatitis (21.6%), transient hyperpigmentation (8.2%), no severe complications

Figure 1: The Study selection process based on the PRISMA guidelines 2020.

CONCLUSION

This systematic review highlights that multimodal, early, and Combination-based treatments gives the most long-lasting and effective Treatment of hypertrophic scars and keloids. Radiotherapy Following surgical ablation specifically When delivered quickly, it remains the most useful tool for recurrence prevention. Laser-supported steroid therapy and intralesional drug combinations delivered good non-surgical alternatives. Monotherapies like cryotherapy or vitamin D injections may act as supportive but are less effective alone. Future large-scale randomized trials are essential to Regulate treatment algorithms Based on patient profile, lesion site and biological activity.

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